

I. CODED EXTRACTS FROM BRAZILIAN CENSUSES

TABLE I: Positives identified in Brazilian censuses

Reference	Quotation	Code
[1, p.78]	“(...) high consumption of digital games in Brazil.”	C3
	“(...) believe that Brazil has a promising market to be explored.”	C3
	“About the national production, we highlight the high production and technical quality of the games.”	C7
	“The associations and regional groups formed around the issues (...)”	C4
	“(...) both for the possibilities of exchange of experiences between market actors (...)”	C6
	“The possibility of having greater prominence on the national scene (...)”	C9
[1, p.79]	“The investment in education in the sector (...)”	C6
	“They also highlight the high technical capacity of the professionals and (...)”	C6
[1, p.108]	“The knowledge and technical competence of the professionals in the sector (...)”	C6
	“The receipt of support from different instances: governmental from the three spheres (municipal, state and federal) and from mainly regional associations.”	C4, C8
	“The events, albeit with caveats about being centralized in a few regions.”	C9
	“The edicts, which are mentioned as a positive aspect even though criticisms and suggestions appear.”	C3
	“Brazilian market with its potential.”	C3
[1, p.137]	“(...) the fact that the industry is growing and that there is a sense of unity among developers, who end up helping each other.”	C4
[1, p.159]	“On the strengths of the industry, freelancers highlighted its growth in recent years beyond the large consumer market for digital games that is Brazil.”	C3, C9
	“They also highlighted that developers in the country are united and often support each other with ideas for projects, advice on the market and the like.”	C4
[1, p.160]	“Supporting organizations also highlight the importance of events as a strength (...)”	C9
	“For both the supporting organizations and the developers the large Brazilian consumer market is perceived in all its importance (...)”	C3
	“The developers, specifically, highlight the high production regime of IBJD beyond its creative potential: they emphasize that Brazilian companies and professionals have great ideas and that their execution takes place by great technical quality and in large scale throughout the country.”	C6, C7
	“Developers recognize national-level or regional-level associations as a strength (...)”	C9
	“Finally, developers perceive that there is improvement in the investment and supply of higher and technical education focused on the digital games sector (...)”	C6

TABLE II: Negatives identified in Brazilian censuses

Reference	Quotation	Code
[1, p.79]	“The degree of current taxation and taxation is one of the most cited weaknesses (...)”	C5, C8
	“A lot of red tape in opening and maintaining business here in Brazil is also mentioned by a lot of developers.”	C8
	“(...) the insufficiency of governmental actions, whether public policies, support or incentives, such as incentives to research in the sector.”	C3, C8
	“(...) the establishment and monitoring of rules of the edicts and awards should be reviewed, for better framing of all categories of the digital games sector.”	C3
	“The lack of professional maturity can also be the cause of the little knowledge in business administration (...)”	C6, C7
	“(...) there is the difficulty of formalizing workers and securing their rights under the CLT, both because of the cost and the current short supply of labor.”	C3, C5, C12
	“The prejudice and little understanding of the digital games sector and its potential (...) This relationship is also a weak point due to the lack of knowledge of the digital games sector by these other areas, which hinders the exchange of knowledge.”	C3, C4, C9
	“On the events, the developers point out that they are rather centralized, as well as poorly publicized and restricted to some extent.”	C3, C4, C9

TABLE II: Negatives identified in Brazilian censuses (continued)

Reference	Quotation	Code
	“Finally, developers comment on how difficult it can be to compete with larger, established companies in the marketplace (...).”	C3, C9
[1, p.108]	“Few training, capacity building and professionalization courses.”	C6
	“Resources centralized in few regions (courses, edicts, investments, government actions).”	C3, C6, C8
	“High bureaucracy to create, formalize and maintain companies and employees.”	C9, C10
	“Unprepared workforce, either in technical terms or in behavioral terms (immaturity at work).”	C6
	“Little job offer and difficulty with the various hiring modalities.”	C3, C10
	“Little information and guidance for companies regarding business management issues (legislation, taxation).”	C6
	“Lack of preparation regarding the international market.”	C3, C9
[1, p.137]	“(…) point out the shortage of vacancies within companies, among other things, which is exacerbated by the tax situation (...).”	C3, C5, C8
	“(…) this product, in turn, becomes costly due to high taxation on the importation of equipment and materials.”	C5, C8, C11
	“Consequently, it is observed how the end consumer ends up having to pay for a product that is several times more expensive, which may not be attractive.”	C1, C5
	“They also report that there is still a lot of prejudice from the population and the government with the sector (...).”	C8, C9
	“They report a lack of contact with publishers and with investors, as well as little business and management knowledge.”	C4, C6
	“They also highlight that the number of edicts is low for individual professionals (...).”	C3
[1, p.157]	“Developers often note that the high tax burden and maintenance costs of a formalized company in often make it difficult to continue in business (...).”	C2, C8, C9
	“(…) it is common for professionals to need to sustain the business with proceeds from other jobs, (...) or other sources of income, such as loans from friends and family or donations.”	C2
	“Developers also consider government actions to the digital games sector as scarce and insufficient.”	C8
	“Although the public notices have increased in recent years, (...) the demand of the sector is much higher than the supply.”	C3, C9
	“In addition, there may be a lack of knowledge of the public policies that can serve the sector, as well as how they can access them.”	C3, C8
[1, p.158]	“This audience also pointed out the great prejudice that exists about digital games in general (...).”	C3
	“(…) difficult competition with larger and already consolidated companies in the market.”	C3, C9
	“Bureaucracy is a perceived factor (...). Mention is also made of the bureaucracy involved in maintaining businesses, such as in administration processes, accountability and tax reporting, and framing issues, for example.”	C7, C8
	“(…) the professionals of the Brazilian digital games industry or related areas are still immature. (...) digital games professionals are unaware of routines and services coming from related areas, such as finance and market vision or legal issues, for example, writing and monitoring contracts, intellectual property protection and others.”	C6
	“(…) the timing of low labor supply coupled with the shortage of mature professionals (...). This may drive the more experienced and mature professionals to other countries.”	C6, C12
[1, p.159]	“(…) IBDJ is still unprepared overall when compared to the international market, both with respect to business vision (in the management of the company itself or the role of that company in the national or international market), and resource management.”	C3, C5, C6
	“Little information and guidance regarding business management is a perceived factor (...).”	C6
	“(…) the bias towards the digital games sector, but they emphasized it on the part of the government overall.”	C3, C8
	“Probably because of the cost that may be involved in attending the exchange events with industry players, (...) as it may be difficult for the category to get contact with investors, publishers and other important industry players.”	C1, C4, C5
	“(…) low chances of competition in funding edicts.”	C2, C3

TABLE III: Opportunities identified in Brazilian censuses

Reference	Quotation	Code
[2, p.69]	“Sell Products/Profit/Raise Capital.”	C2
	“Establish yourself in the market/Succeed/Maintain stable capital.”	C2, C9
	“Expand market/Attract new customers/Expand business.”	C1, C3, C9
	“Reach international market.”	C3
	“Focus/generate own products.”	C7, C9
	“Develop for new platforms/Consolidate on platform.”	C7
	“Improve quality/quantity of production.”	C7
	“Survive.”	C2
	“Improve and/or expand manpower/management.”	C6, C10
[1, p.82]	“Taxation and taxation.”	C5, C8
	“Bureaucracy. (...) The process of opening and maintaining a business requires the monitoring and fulfillment of many administrative routines, which can inhibit or even discourage the founding of businesses on national soil (...).”	C8, C9
	“In the absence of good workforce preparation environments, it can become even more difficult to build good teams required for the management and development of large digital game projects.”	C6, C7, C10
	“Find and retain skilled professionals.”	C6, C10
	“Working/Contracting Regime. (...) The opportunity is to be able to afford the big cost that this entails, especially for those developers who are starting out.”	C5, C10
	“Business administration routines. It is observed that the professional who has undertaken in the area of digital games has little notions about the administrative routines that a business requires (...).”	C6
[1, p.83]	“Identify player profile, target audience and how to build loyalty.”	C1
	“Profitability and high costs. (...) There are developers who say it is a opportunity to keep the business profitable and self-sufficient. It is also difficult to keep the business going with the current high cost of good equipment for manufacturing and realizing on-demand or developer-owned projects.”	C2, C5, C7, C11
	“The costs of attending events are also usually quite onerous. Developers generally say that the cost of major travel to the locations where major events take place is a opportunity (...).”	C1, C5
	“Maintain constant development activities. This maintenance seems to suffer difficulties because the businesses for the most part are still unprofitable. Because of this, the partners and also the workers of the developers often need to engage in other activities to maintain themselves financially, and also manage to maintain the company.”	C2, C7, C12
	“Own copyrighted projects and intellectual property. (...) The respondents report that it is great difficulty to find information or professionals who know the legislation (...).”	C7, C6, C9
[1, p.109]	“Taxation and taxation, (...) are also highlighted by organizations supporting development and services in digital games.”	C5, C8
	“The difficult access to equipment such as the entire set of software and hardware (...) directly hinders the work of solutions that organizations can provide, but also because it can even be a demotivating factor and makes it a opportunity to keep good professionals in the country, as well as decreasing international competitiveness.”	C3, C7, C9, C10, C11
	“(…) retaining highly skilled professionals is a complicated task, both now and in the coming years, because working conditions are still difficult in the domestic digital games industry. Right now the configurations of the national industry are problematic because they make it difficult, for example, to formalize these professionals - which ends up making acting in the foreign market more advantageous.”	C3, C6, C9, C12
	“Decision between frameworks and all the bureaucracy involved for creating and maintaining companies are often mentioned as problems and opportunities.”	C9
[1, p.110]	“Poorly qualified/skilled professionals are a current problem and something classified as a opportunity (...) as the formation of partnerships is hampered if there are few knowledgeable digital games industry people in the market in the related areas of knowledge (...).”	C6, C10

TABLE III: Opportunities identified in Brazilian censuses (continued)

Reference	Quotation	Code
	“Lack of necessary knowledge and guidance for business management is another current problem and a opportunity for the future of IBJD, which still seems to be immature on this topic. Routines of maintaining the company and its exercise, keeping accounts current, and managing human resources are among the difficulties listed.”	C6, C7
[1, p.138]	“The main problems mentioned (...) was regarding taxation and taxation, the difficulty of accessing equipment for product development, and the difficulty of forming and maintaining teams. They also consider that more investments and tax incentives are needed (...)”	C2, C7, C8, C10, C11
[1, p.162]	“The issue of high taxation and taxation is quite apparent (...). Investment in tools for development or for supporting the digital games industry is still expensive, even when the equipment is donated and comes from abroad.”	C5, C8, C11
	“The bureaucracy was also quite cited (...) It seems to influence in some of the next problems pointed out, as in the framing in calls for proposals, in the opening of business maintenance or in the internalization of equipment and resources coming from abroad.”	C3, C9, C11, C12
	“(…) it is difficult to comply with the criteria proposed in the funding edicts. (...) the opening of a company is the main obstacle to plead for public funding, for example.”	C2, C3, C9
[1, p.163]	“(…) the digital games sector is still incipient in the country: few professionals in the areas of law (tax, international, etc.) know the regulations that the sector uses (...). There is still mutual ignorance of support and development activities, which hinders the sector’s maturation and limits international competitiveness.”	C3, C6, C7, C9
	“This lack of knowledge has as a consequence the shortage of ”highly qualified” professionals, as well as creates an unmatured industry that has difficulty retaining such professionals in the country (...)”	C6, C9, C10
	“For freelancers it is difficult to find partners in the various areas of production and development that a digital game demands; plus it is not easy to also realize partnerships in related areas.”	C4, C7

REFERENCES

- [1] L. O. Sakuda and I. Fortim, *II Census of the Brazilian Digital Games Industry*, 2018, (in Portuguese). [Online]. Available: http://www.abragames.org/uploads/5/6/8/0/56805537/af-iicenso-summary_2.pdf
- [2] A. Fleury, D. Nakano, and J. Cordeiro, *I Census of the Brazilian Digital Games Industry*, 2014, (in Portuguese). [Online]. Available: http://www.abragames.org/uploads/5/6/8/0/56805537/i_censo_da_industria_brasileira_de_jogos_digitais_2.pdf